

Gryon nixon Masner (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae): a new egg parasite of Leptocorisa oratorius in the Philippines

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Two egg parasites of the rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius* (= *L. acuta* in the reports of Uichanco 1921, 1949; Otones and Sison 1941) have been recorded in the Philippines:

- 1) *Ooencyrtus malayensis* Ferriere (Encyrtidae)
- 2) *Telenomus comperei* Crawford (Scelionidae).

In a 1978-79 field trial at IRRI to compare the natural enemy abundance in weekly and biannual cropping patterns without insecticide, an egg parasite of *L. oratorius* was found new to the Philippines. The study used rice cultivars IR36 and IR1917 from October 1978 to January 1979. Potted mature plants laden with 1-day-old eggs of *L. oratorius* from a greenhouse colony were placed in the field at weekly intervals from flowering to hard dough stages of the field crop.

After 4 days' exposure in the field, the eggs were incubated in the laboratory in small, sealed, glass vials with moisture provided in a wad of cotton. Parasitization was probably higher in the continuously cropped fields (16 and 29%) than in the biannually cropped fields (4 and 18%) (see table). The scelionid parasite, identified by the senior author as *Gryon nixon* Masner (= *Hadronotus flavipes* Ashmead and *leptocorisae* Nixon), is also recorded in India, Indonesia, Malaysia, and Papua New Guinea. The adult is 1.25 mm long and black except for hyaline wings, yellow-brown legs, reddish to dark brown antennae, coxae, and tarsal segment V, and with a pale yellow stigmal vein (see figure).

Parasitization of rice bug eggs by <i>Gryon nixon</i> Masner obtained by exposing potted plants laden with <i>Leptocorisa oratorius</i> eggs in a portion of a weekly-cropped area planted the same week as biannual fields of IR36 and IR1917 without insecticide. IRRI. 1978-79.				
Cropping system	Cultivar	Eggs exposed (no.)	Parasitized eggs (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Weekly	IR36	589	173	29
Biannual	IR36	288	52	18
Weekly	IR1917	147	23	16
Biannual	IR1917	213	9	4

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